

Systematic Review Study on Emotional Intelligence, Academic Self-concept and Academic Procrastination

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Emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination are important psychological constructs that influence students' academic behaviour and learning outcomes. Emotional intelligence refers to an individual's ability to pursue, understand and regulate emotions effectively in one and others while academic self-concept reflects students' perception and belief about their academic abilities and competence. Academic procrastination, on the other hand, refers to the tendency to intentionally delay academic tasks such as studying, completing assignments or preparing for examinations despite being aware of possible negative consequences. Over the years, researchers have increasingly emphasized the role of emotional and cognitive factors in shaping students' engagement with academic tasks and their overall academic performance. Previous results suggest that students with higher levels of emotional intelligence are better able to regulate stress, manage negative emotions and maintain motivation when dealing with academic challenges. Similarly, students who possess positive academic self-concept tend to demonstrate greater confidence, persistence and involvement in learning activities. In contrast, academic procrastination has been associated with emotional regulation difficulties, low academic confidence and ineffective management strategies. The present review aims to examine and synthesize existing research on the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination. Using a systematic review approach guided by the PRISMA framework, studies from both Indian and international contexts were examined to understand how the psychological construct interacts with academic settings. The review indicates that emotional intelligence contributes to affective emotional regulation and coping strategy concepts and reduces the tendency to procrastinate. Importance of emotional competencies and positive academic self-perception in promoting better academic engagement and reducing procrastination behaviour among students.

Keywords: Systematic review study, emotional intelligence, academic self-concept, and academic procrastination

Educational achievement is influenced not only by cognitive abilities but also by various psychological and emotional factors that shape students' attitudes and behaviour towards learning. Among these factors, emotional intelligence, academic and self-concept have received considerable attention in educational psychology. Emotional intelligence refers to an individual's ability to recognise, understand and regulate emotion effectively in oneself and others. Students who possess higher emotional intelligence are generally better able to manage academic stress, maintain motivation and adapt to challenging academic situations (MacCann et al., 2020; Chamizo-Nieto et al., 2021). The concept that reflects students' perception and belief about their own academic abilities also plays an important role in engagement and performance. Students with a positive academic self-concept tend to display greater confidence, persistence and willingness to participate in academic activities (Guo et al., 2017; Respondek et al., 2020).

In contrast, academic procrastination represents a common behavioural challenge among students across different educational levels. Academic procrastination research to the intentional delay of academic tasks despite knowing that such delay will lead to negative academic consequences (Steel, 2007). Research has shown that procrastination is often associated with emotional regulation difficulties, fear of failure and low academic confidence (Steel, 2007; Deniz et al., 2009). Students who struggle to manage negative emotions or put forth their academic abilities may postpone academic tasks to avoid stress or anxiety related to academic work (Tice & Baumeister, 1997; Steel, 2007). Understanding the relationship between emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination is therefore important in identifying the psychological factors that influence students' academic behaviour. Examine how emotional competencies and self-perceptions contribute to students' academic engagement and their ability to manage academic responsibility effectively.

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Method

The present study employed a systematic review approach to examine the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination. The review was conducted in accordance with the general guidelines of the PRISMA framework to ensure a structured and transparent selection of relevant studies. Research articles were identified through electronic academic databases such as Research Gate, Google Scholar, Scopus, ERIC, and PsycINFO using keyword “emotional intelligence, “academic self-concept”, “academic procrastination” and “students”. Only peer-reviewed studies published in English and

focusing on student population were included in the review. Titles and abstracts of the identified studies were screened to determine their relevance, after which the selected articles were examined in detail. The findings from both Indian and international studies were then organized and synthesized to understand the relationship among the three constructs.

Review of Literature

The present section is divided into three categories based on variables.

The Interplay between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Self-concept Indian Research

Research conducted in the Indian context has increasingly emphasized the relationship between emotional intelligence and students' perceptions of their academic abilities. Several studies indicate that emotional competence plays a significant role in shaping how students evaluate their own academic potential and self-worth. For instance, the study conducted by Singh and Singh (2012) college students reported a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-concept, suggesting that students who are better able to understand and regulate their emotions tend to develop stronger confidence in their academic abilities. Similar findings were reported by Kaur and Maheshwari (2015) who found that adolescents with higher emotional intelligence also demonstrated higher levels of esteem and self-awareness. These emotional skills were found to contribute to more positive academic self-perception. In another study (Kumar, 2016).

Investigated secondary school students and found that emotional intelligence was positively associated with several dimensions of self-concept, including educational and intellectual self-concept indicating that emotionally competent students tend to evaluate their academic abilities more positively.

Further research in India continues to support this association. Koneri and Roopmala (2017) reported a strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-concept among higher secondary school students, suggesting that emotional awareness and emotional regulation may strengthen students' belief in their academic competency. Similarly, Sahoo (2017) found that emotional intelligence contributed to students' positive self-evaluation and increased engagement in academic activity. An analytical review conducted by Srinivasan et al. (2018) also confirms that emotional intelligence is positively associated with academic achievement, indicating that emotionally competent students are more likely to develop confidence in their academic abilities. More recently, Mohanty and Pandey (2023) found a strong positive association between emotional intelligence and self-concept among high school students across various democratic groups. Conceptual work such as Lavalekar (2024) has further highlighted emotional awareness and self-control, which are central components of emotional intelligence that contribute to the development of a balanced, positive self-concept among students.

Summary

Overall, the Indian studies reviewed indicate a consistent positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic self-concept among students. Most of the research suggests that students who possess higher emotional intelligence tend to develop stronger

self-perception of their academic abilities. Emotional competencies such as self-awareness, emotional regulation and empathy help students manage academic challenges more effectively, which contribute to a more positive academic self-concept. Studies conducted across different student populations, including secondary School student adolescence and college students, largely support this association. These findings highlight the importance of emotional intelligence as a psychological factor that contributes to students' confidence, self-belief and overall academic adjustment.

International Research

Research conducted outside India has also extensively examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic self-concept among students. Early studies emphasize the place of emotional intelligence and its important role in shaping students' emotional awareness, well-being and perception of competence. For instance, Márquez et al. (2006) examined high school students using the Mayor Salovey Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test and found that emotional intelligence contributed positively to academic functioning and students' self-perception of their abilities. Similarly, Zautra et al. (2008) reported that emotional attentiveness, which is a component of emotional intelligence, was associated with higher levels of positive affect and life satisfaction factors that contribute to the development of a positive self-concept. Subsequent studies continued to highlight the relationship of the Yuksel et al. (2014) examine vocational high school students and found that emotional intelligence was associated with psychological characteristics such as self-actualization and social responsibility, which are closely related to students' self-perception and personal development Sánchez Álvarez et al. (2016) Also reported opposite relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological will been suggesting that individuals with higher emotional intelligence 10 to half greater self-acceptance and more positive view of themselves. More recent studies further reinforce the importance of emotional intelligence in academic context. Maciver et al. (2018) reported that emotional intelligence and self-concept both play an important role in academic performance and overall academic adjustment among students. Herrera et al. (2020) also found that academic self-concept was a significant predictor of academic outcome among primary school students from different cultural backgrounds. In addition, a large-scale matter analysis conducted by MacCann et al. (2020) involving more than 40000 participants found an opposite association between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. These findings collectively suggest that emotional intelligence contributes to students' academic development by enhancing emotional regulation, confidence and positive perception of their academic abilities.

Summary of International research

Overall, indicate the opposite relationship between emotional intelligence and academic self-concept among students. Many studies suggest that students who possess higher emotional intelligence tend to have better emotional awareness, stronger confidence in their abilities and more positive perception of themselves. Emotional intelligence helps students regulate emotions and manage academic experience. As a result, emotionally intelligent students are more likely to develop a stronger academic self-concept and demonstrate better academic adjustment and performance.

Interplay between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Procrastination Indian Research

Research conducted in India has increasingly explored how emotional intelligence influences students' tendency to delay academic tasks. Early studies highlighted the role of emotional competency in improving students' motivation and engagement in academic activities. For instance, Kumar (2019) examined higher secondary school students and found that emotional intelligence was positively related to academic achievement motivation. The finding suggested that students who possess higher emotional intelligence tend to demonstrate stronger motivation toward completing academic tasks, which may indirectly reduce Procrastination behaviour. Similarly, Chithral et al. (2019) conducted a study on postgraduate psychology students and reported that emotional intelligence may be positively associated with academic achievement. The study found that different dimensions of emotional intelligence including self-recognition, self-regulation, empathy and relationship management, were positively related to better academic outcomes indicating that emotional scale plays an important role in students' academic engagement.

Subsequent studies examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and Procrastination tendencies among students. Abid and Khan (2021) conducted research on undergraduate and postgraduate students and reported that emotional intelligence had a significant negative influence on academic procrastination, suggesting that emotionally intelligent students are less likely to delay academic tasks. Similarly, Kumar and Sharma (2023) investigated young adults and observed variation in emotional intelligence across demographic groups emphasizing the role of emotional competencies in students' academic adjustment. More recently, Sayeed and Srivastava (2025) found a significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and academic procrastination among university students, indicating that emotionally intelligent students tend to experience lower levels of academic stress and are less likely to postpone their academic responsibilities. In addition, Agarwal and Rajan (2025) reported that emotional intelligence was negatively associated with academic procrastination among college students, with life satisfaction acting as a mediating factor in their relationship.

Summary of Indian Researchers

Overall, Indian studies largely indicate a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and academic procrastination among students. Research suggests that students with higher emotional intelligence tend to demonstrate better emotional regulation, greater academic motivation and improved coping strategies when dealing with academic demands. These emotional competencies help students manage stress and negative emotions effectively, thereby reducing their tendency to delay academic tasks and promoting more productive academic behaviour.

Review of International research

Research conducted outside India has also examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic procrastination among students. Early studies emphasize that Procrastination is often linked to difficulties in emotional regulation and self-management. For instance, Deniz, Ras, and Aydogan (2009) investigated university students and found a significant negative

relationship between emotional intelligence and academic procrastination. Their findings indicated that students who possess higher emotional intelligence are better able to regulate negative emotions such as anxiety and frustration, which reduces their tendency to delay academic tasks. Similarly, Hen and Goroshit (2012) examined college students with and without learning disabilities and reported that emotional intelligence had an indirect negative influence on academic procrastination. The studies showed that emotional intelligence strengthens students' academic self-efficacy, which in turn reduces procrastination behaviour.

Later studies continued to support the importance of emotional intelligence in academic settings. Ahmad (2013) reported a negative association between emotional intelligence and procrastination among intermediate science students suggesting that students who can effectively manage negative moods are less likely to postpone academic responsibilities. More recent research has also confirmed this relationship. MacCann et al. (2020) conducted a large-scale meta-analysis and reported that emotional intelligence contributes to better academic performance and academic adjustment, indicating that emotional competencies help students manage academic challenges more effectively. Similarly, Sánchez -Gómez et al. (2023) and Alizadeh et al. (2023) found that emotional intelligence was negatively related to academic procrastination among university students, with factors such as self-efficacy and emotional regulation playing an important mediating role. These findings collectively suggest that emotional intelligence functions as a protective psychological factor that helps students regulate emotions and reduce the likelihood of procrastination.

Summary of International research

Overall, international research indicates a consistent negative relationship between emotional intelligence and academic procrastination among students. The reviewed studies suggest that emotional intelligence plays an important role in helping students regulate their emotions, manage academic stress and maintain motivation when dealing with academic tasks. Students who possess higher emotional intelligence are generally better able to cope up with feelings such as anxiety, frustration and fear of failure, which often contribute to procrastination behaviour. As a result, emotionally intelligent students tend to approach academic tasks more effectively and are less likely to delay their academic responsibilities.

Academic Procrastination and Academic Self-concept Indian Research

Research conducted in India has examined the relationship between students' academic self-concept and their tendency to procrastinate in academic tasks. Early studies highlighted that students' beliefs about their academic abilities significantly influence their academic behaviour. For instance, Babu et al. (2019) examined the relationship between self-esteem and academic procrastination among dental students and found that students with lower levels of self-esteem were more likely to delay academic tasks. All the relationships reported were relatively weak; the finding suggested that students' perception of their academic competency may influence their tendency to postpone their responsibilities. Similarly, Kumar and Basheer (2021) investigated college students and reported an inverse relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination. The studies suggested that students who

possess stronger beliefs in their academic abilities tend to engage more actively in academic tasks and are less likely to procrastinate.

More recent studies have further supported this relationship. Rao et al. (2023) conducted research among psychology students and found a negative correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination, indicating that students with higher academic confidence were less likely to delay academic tasks. Saha et al. (2024) examined undergraduate medical students and reported a significant negative relationship between self-esteem and academic procrastination, suggesting that students with stronger positive self-perception tend to demonstrate lower levels of procrastination. In addition, Parveen et al. (2024) investigated adolescents and found that academic procrastination was inversely related to self-efficacy, with students who believed in their academic abilities showing a lower level of task engagement daily. These findings collectively indicate that student academic self-beliefs play an important role in shaping their academic behaviour and reducing procrastination tendencies.

Summary

Overall, Indian research suggests that academic self-concept and related constructs such as self-esteem and self-efficacy are negatively associated with academic procrastination among students. Studies consistently indicate that students who possess stronger beliefs in academic abilities are more likely to engage actively in academic tasks and are less likely to delay their academic responsibilities. A positive academic self-concept, therefore, appears to function as an important motivational factor that helps reduce procrastination behaviour among students.

International Research

Research conducted in an international context has also examined the relationship between students' perception of their academic abilities and their tendency to procrastinate in academic tasks. Early theoretical and empirical studies emphasize that procrastination is closely related to students' beliefs about their competency and their ability to complete academic work. For instance, Steel (2007) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis on procrastination and reported that procrastination is strongly associated with low self-efficacy and fear of failure. According to this perspective, students who doubt their academic abilities are more likely to delete tasks to temporarily avoid anxiety or the possibility of failure. Similarly, Hajloo (2014) examined undergraduate psychology students and found that procrastination was negatively correlated with both self-efficacy and self-esteem. The studies suggested that students who possess stronger confidence and have better academic abilities tend to approach academic tasks more and are less likely to postpone their responsibilities.

Subsequent research has continued to support the relationship between academic self-concept and academic procrastination behaviour. Studies have indicated that students who possess stronger academic self-concept tend to demonstrate higher levels of motivation, persistence and engagement in academic activities. Conversely, students who hold negative perceptions of their academic competency experience academic anxiety and self-doubt, which contribute to avoidance behaviour such as procrastination. Recent research has also emphasized that academic self-concept plays an important role in students' academic adjustment and performance, as a positive academic self-belief encourages

students to initiate tasks, maintain effort and persevere in the face of challenges. This finding suggests that a student about their academic competency is closely linked to their ability to manage academic responsibilities effectively and avoid procrastination behaviours.

Summary

Overall, international research indicates a negative relationship between academic self-concept and academic procrastination among students. Studies consistently suggest that students who possess stronger beliefs in their academic abilities tend to demonstrate higher levels of motivation and academic engagement, which reduces their tendency to delay academic self-perception and are more likely to experience anxiety and avoid behaviour that contributes to procrastination.

Conclusion

The present review examined the relationships among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination by synthesizing findings from both Indian and international research. The study reviewed indicates that emotional intelligence plays an important role in helping students regulate emotions, manage academic stress and maintain motivation in academic settings. Students who possess higher emotional intelligence tend to demonstrate better emotional control and coping strategies, which positively influence their academic behaviour. Similarly, academic self-concept has been identified as a significant factor that shapes students' confidence, their academic abilities and their engagement with learning tasks. Students with stronger academic backgrounds display greater persistence and willingness to complete academic responsibilities.

The literature also suggests that academic procrastination is closely associated with emotional and cognitive factors. Students who have trouble in regulating emotions or who have lower confidence in their academic abilities are more likely to postpone academic tasks. In contrast, emotionally intelligent students with positive academic self-concept are better equipped to approach academic challenges and are less likely to engage in procrastination. Overall, the findings highlight that emotional intelligence and academic self-concept function as important psychological resources that can reduce students' tendency toward academic procrastination. Understanding the relationship among these variables can provide useful insight for educators, counselors and researchers in developing strategies that support students' emotional development, strengthen academic self-belief and promote more effective academic engagement.

Limitations of the Study

Although the present review provides useful insight into the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination, several limitations in the existing body of research should be acknowledged. One major limitation observed in the reviewed studies is that many researchers have examined these variables independently rather than investigating their combined interaction. While a few studies focus on emotional intelligence and academic procrastination or academic self-concept and procrastination separately, few studies explore how emotional intelligence and academic self-concept together influence procrastination behaviour. This lack of integrated research limits understanding of complex psychological processes that contribute to

student academic behaviour, in addition to many of the review's studies being primarily on cross-sectional research design and self-report measures, which may introduce bias by restricting the ability to establish causal relationships among the variables.

Another limitation identified through the synthesis of literature is the limited diversity in research contacts and population. A considerable number of studies have been conducted with specific educational settings or among student groups, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Differences in cultural background, educational system and academic environment may influence how emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination interact among students. Furthermore, relatively related research has been conducted within certain regions and educational levels, particularly in developing contexts. These caps indicate that further research is needed using diverse samples and methodological approaches to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination.

Future and Implications of the Study

The gaps identified in existing literature suggest several directions for future Research and educational practice. Future studies may focus on examining the combined relationship among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and academic procrastination in a more integrated manner. Since many previous studies have explored these variables separately, investigating how emotional intelligence and academic self-concept together influence the student's procrastination behaviour could provide a deeper understanding of the psychological mechanism underline academy task delay. In addition, future researchers may employ longitudinal research designs to better understand how these constructions developed and interact over time rather than relying solely on cross-sectional approaches.

Further research may also expand the scope of research by including a diverse student population across different educational levels, disciplines and cultural backgrounds. Conducting studies in varied academic environments may help determine whether the relationships among emotional intelligence, academic self-concept and procrastination remain consistent across different cultural settings. Additionally, future studies may explore intervention programs aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence and strengthening students' academic self-concept in order to reduce procrastination tendencies. Such research provides valuable insight for educators, counsellors and policy makers in developing strategies to start students' emotional development, improve academic confidence and promote more effective academic engagement.

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